

BASIS OF MENTAL HEALTH SUPPORT PROGRAMS IN BACOLOD CITY COLLEGE: A NEEDS ASSESSMENT STUDY

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Basis of Mental Health Support Programs in Bacolod City College: A Needs Assessment Study

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Abstract

Bacolod City College recognizes the importance of mental health for its diverse student body, addressing academic pressures, financial concerns, and social challenges. By identifying priorities, the guidance center can implement proactive measures for effective stress management. The study used a quantitative descriptive design to gather data on the mental health priorities of Bacolod City College students, incorporating factors like age, sex, and living conditions, aligning with the Department of Science and Technology's Mental Health Research Agenda. LGBTQ+ issues were viewed as low priority in this school while suicide/self-harm issues and family issues were seen as a high priority. The Business Administration-Entrepreneurship department also views Abuse and Trauma and HIV and STDs as high-priority mental health issues. The quality of life for older students with mental health issues is generally good, regardless of demographic variables such as sex, living conditions, and parental employment. Mental health issues are well understood by male students, high-income students, and employed parents, with age and sex showing significant differences within-group. The Guidance Center of Bacolod City College should continue to support students with unique mental health concerns, focusing on improving their quality of life and family environment.

Keywords: *mental health support, academic pressures, social challenges, self-harm issues, LGBTQ+*

Introduction

Concerns about college students' mental health and well-being are developing in today's fast-paced, cutthroat academic climate (Komal, 2023). Bacolod City College understands the need to attend to the mental health needs of its student body because it is a diverse institution with students from a range of backgrounds. The purpose of this needs assessment research is to match the guidance center's services and activities to the students' priorities in the college's different departments.

To create focused support programs that can successfully address students' issues, it is essential to understand their priorities for their mental health. Bacolod City College can learn a great deal about the common mental health issues that affect its student body by carrying out a needs assessment study. According to the American Psychological Association (APA) (2024), college students often face a myriad of stressors, including academic pressures, financial concerns, and social challenges, which can significantly impact their mental health.

By identifying the mental health priorities of Bacolod City College students, the guidance center can implement proactive measures to support students in managing these stressors effectively. Moreover, early intervention and targeted support programs can have a positive impact on the mental health outcomes of college students (Colizzi et al., 2020). By conducting a needs assessment study, Bacolod City College can identify areas where additional support is needed and develop evidence-based interventions to address these needs. This proactive approach can help prevent the escalation of mental health issues and promote a culture of well-being on campus.

The primary objectives of this study are: (1) to determine the extent of prioritization of mental health issues by the different students in the 5 departments in Bacolod City College; (2) to assess the differences in the student's degree of Quality of Life (QoL) while living with mental health issues by demographic variables; and, (3) to assess the differences in the degree of how well the students' family environment understands their mental health issues by demographic variables.

This proposed needs assessment study at Bacolod City College is a crucial step towards enhancing the mental health support programs for its diverse student population. By understanding the specific mental health priorities of students, the guidance center can develop tailored interventions that effectively address their needs. This proactive approach not only supports the well-being of students but also contributes to a positive and inclusive campus environment.

Research Questions

The primary objectives of this study are coursed through the following questions:

1. What is the extent of prioritization of mental health issues by the different students in the 5 departments at Bacolod City College?
2. Are there differences in the student's degree of Quality of Life (QoL) while living with mental health issues by demographic variables?
3. Are there differences in the degree of how well the students' family environment understands their mental health issues by demographic variables?

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework. The social ecology model is a significant theoretical framework that can guide a needs assessment study on mental health (Cramer & Kapusta, 2023); and this study has utilized this model as its theoretical framework. This model, created by Bronfenbrenner, highlights how societal, interpersonal, communal, and individual influences are intertwined and influence mental health outcomes (Tong & An, 2024). The researchers of this study can create focused interventions that address the underlying causes of mental health disparities by looking at how these different levels of influence interact and affect mental health needs.

Urie Bronfenbrenner created the Social Ecological Model (SEM). This theoretical framework has been applied extensively in several disciplines, including public health, sociology, and psychology. This model offers a thorough grasp of how various environmental system levels impact humans. The microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem, macrosystem, and chronosystem are the five interrelated systems that make up Bronfenbrenner's SEM (Guy-Evans, 2024). The way that these systems interact influences how people develop and behave. The SEM can be a useful framework for comprehending the several aspects that affect a person's mental health in the context of needs assessment research on mental health. The interconnections between several microsystems in an individual's life are called the mesosystem. A needs assessment study using the Social Ecological Model would consider how demographic variables impact students' access to mental health resources and support.

Conceptual Framework. In this study, independent variables are demographic variables. These are age, sex, living conditions, family income, and employment of parents. Age refers to how old the students are and grouped as Older (≥ 22) or Younger (< 22). Sex refers to the biological sex of the student namely male and female. Living condition refers to who the student is living with; the categories in this variable are Living with Immediate Family, Living with a Relative/ Extended Family, or Living in Apartment/ Dormitory/ Boarding House. Family Income refers to the amount of income the students' family earns per month and it is based on the categories of the Philippine Statistics Authority (2023); the categories in this variable are Poor ($< \text{Php } 12,030$ per month), Low Income (Php 12,030 - Php 24,060 per month), Lower-Middle Income (Php 24,060 - Php 48,120 per month), and High Income ($> \text{Php } 144,000$ per month). Lastly, the Employment of Parents refers to who among the students' parents earns for the family; the categories in this variable are: Both Employed, Both Unemployed; Care-off Guardian/ No Parents; One (1) Working Parent. When the research participant ticks both unemployed, the student is more likely a working student or another member of the family earns for the family, while if the research participant ticks care-off guardian, the student is more likely to get finances from their next of kin.

In this study, the dependent variables are as follows: (1) the extent of prioritization of mental health issues refers to how important a mental health issue is according to the student's personal opinion, (2) Quality of Life (QoL) when living with Mental Health refers to the degree of how well the students' quality of life is while living with a mental health issue; lastly, (3) Family Environment refers to the degree of how well the students' family environment understands their mental health issues.

Methodology

Research Design

A quantitative descriptive design was used in the study to collect information on the mental health priorities of Bacolod City College students. This design allows the analysis of numerical data. This makes it possible to spot patterns and trends, which helps with the creation of focused assistance programs.

Participants

Bacolod City College students served as the participants of this research to collect information on their mental health priorities. There are five departments of the college which is proportionally represented by a sample size that was taken using stratified random sampling.

Instruments

A researcher-made instrument was used to gather the survey data wherein its content was aligned with the Mental Health Research Agenda of the Department of Science and Technology (2023). A panel of experts was invited to rate the face validity of the instrument, via the Good and Scates Method, which resulted in excellent validity (4.30). Internal Consistency was computed for reliability wherein an initial 30 people, not included in the final sample data, were used to determine Cronbach's alpha (0.89).

Procedure

After seeking clearance from the leading school key persons, an online (google) form was used where students may answer. The form was opened for about a month from March to April 2024. Students were able to answer the survey within the allotted time. Additionally, demographic information was collected to understand how factors such as age, sex, and other factors may influence mental health priorities.

Data Analysis

Although means and standard deviations are utilized to characterize data, they are simply verbally described in this paper to streamline the data presentation. When the data was tested for normality using Shapiro-Wilk, it was discovered that the data were not normally

distributed; as a result, non-parametric tests were employed for all inferential statistical procedures. However, for the Quality of Life (QoL) and Attitude towards mental health variables, data shows normal distribution and equal variances. Hence, they will utilize the ANOVA test.

Ethical Considerations

All participants gave their informed consent, guaranteeing that they were aware of the study's objectives and their legal rights as research subjects. Respect was shown for maintaining anonymity and confidentiality, and data was securely stored with only authorized personnel having access. Participants' well-being was thoroughly evaluated for any possible dangers, and suitable support services were provided.

Results and Discussion

The Extent of Prioritization of Mental Health Issues Per Department. Even though the various departments at Bacolod City College view most mental health issues as “neutrally prioritized”, Table 1 below shows that some topics appear to be given a low or high extent of priority. The Office Administration and Teacher Education Departments view LGBTQ+ issues as low priority (M=2.48, SD=1.44). The Business Administration-Entrepreneurship and Industrial Technology Departments view suicide/self-harm issues (M=3.71, SD=1.57; M=3.70, SD=1.44, respectively) and family issues (M=3.52, SD=1.58; M=3.70, SD=1.58, respectively) as a high priority. Depression and Anxiety, as a mental health issue, were given high priority by the Information Systems Department (M=3.53, SD=1.66), Teacher Education Department (M=3.43, SD=1.41), Business Administration-Entrepreneurship Department (M=4.54, SD=1.04), and Industrial Technology department (M=4.00, SD=1.29). Lastly, the Business Administration-Entrepreneurship department also views Abuse and Trauma (M=3.48, SD=1.48), and HIV and STDs (M=3.56, SD=1.64) as high-priority mental health issues.

Table 1. Extent of Prioritization of Mental Health Issues Per Department

Mental Health Issues	Office Administration	Information Systems- ACT	Teacher Educ action	Business Administration & Entrep	Industrial Tech
Suicide and non-suicidal	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	High Priority	High Priority
Self-injury	Priority	Priority	Priority		
Depression and Anxiety	Neutral	High Priority	High Priority	High Priority	High Priority
Psychosis	Priority Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral
Psychosocial Problems	Priority Neutral	Priority Neutral	Priority Neutral	Priority Neutral	Priority Neutral
due to Life Crisis	Priority	Priority	Priority	Priority	Priority
Abuse and Trauma	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	High Priority	Neutral
LGBTQ+ Issues	Priority Low Priority	Priority Neutral	Priority Low Priority	Neutral	Priority Neutral
HIV and STDs	Neutral	Priority Neutral	Neutral	Priority High Priority	Priority Neutral
Non-communicable	Priority Neutral	Priority Neutral	Priority Neutral	Neutral	Priority Neutral
Disease	Priority	Priority	Priority	Priority	Priority
Family Issues	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	High Priority	High Priority
Substance Abuse	Priority Neutral	Priority Neutral	Priority Neutral	Neutral	Neutral
	Priority	Priority	Priority	Priority	Priority

Note. A mean of more than 3.41 indicates "High Priority", while a mean of less than 2.61 indicates "Low Priority".

The data presented in Table 1 indicate a difference in priorities across the educational fields, which means that students from all departments are exposed to different stress levels and challenges. This diversity of priorities could indicate that each student is confronted with unique emotional and academic demands, which emphasizes the importance of individual mental health care in each

department. This highlights the need for this study to assess and monitor the extent of prioritization of mental health issues within departments to ensure that students receive relevant and effective support that addresses their unique challenges and stressors.

LGBTQ+ concerns are given low priority in the Office Administration and Teacher Education departments, which may indicate that students in these fields do not view these issues as having a direct bearing on their personal or academic lives. This might be the result of their professions' lack of exposure to or knowledge of LGBTQ+ issues (Martin-Storey & Fish, 2019). This might perhaps reflect how little attention institutions or society at a large place on these issues. LGBTQ+ issues might not receive the same attention or inclusion in the curriculum as they do in other academic subjects (Moore, 2016). On the other hand, the Teacher Education department lists depression and anxiety as top priorities, signifying that students in this department deal with issues related to stress from the classroom and job preparation (Travers & Cooper, 2018). Additionally, it is in line with the body of research that emphasizes the pressures of student teaching, lesson planning, classroom management, and other aspects of being ready for the teaching profession (McCarthy et al., 2019). Support structures must be in place for those in this field because these pressures have the potential to worsen mental health issues.

The Business Administration, Entrepreneurship, and Industrial Technology departments place high priority on suicide and non-suicidal self-injury, as well as on family concerns. This could be due to the competitive nature of these professions and the pressures placed on students to achieve well academically. In the study, Seaward (2020), said that this could be because of the demanding academic schedules, potential career paths, and the fast-paced nature of these professions. Stress of this kind can worsen mental health issues, including worries about family relationships and self-harm. Furthermore, the high priority given to HIV and STDs, abuse and trauma, and depression and anxiety in these departments emphasizes the difficulty of the challenges that students may encounter and the necessity of comprehensive support systems that address these challenging issues.

Lastly, the high priority given by the Information Systems department to depression and anxiety indicates that students may have experienced significant stressors related to the fast-paced and demanding nature of their field. Students may find it difficult to keep up with the demands of their skill sets, the fast-changing technologies, and the demanding coursework (Beiter et al., 2015). However, they also rank other mental health concerns as neutral, demonstrating a general awareness of them but a lack of emphasis on them. This may point to the need for more training and awareness programs to address and comprehend the entire range of mental health concerns that everyone in this field may encounter. Bacolod City College can better address the unique requirements of students in various departments and advance general well-being by concentrating on these areas when developing its mental health support services.

Based on Table 1 data, Bacolod City College needs to develop mental health support services that are specifically designed to address the needs and concerns of students in various academic departments. Suicide, self-harm, and family issues, for example, are highly prioritized in departments like Business Administration-Entrepreneurship and Industrial Technology, indicating that students in these fields face unique stressors related to academic performance and industry expectations (Lipson et al., 2016). Furthermore, the high priority placed by these departments on HIV and STDs, depression, anxiety, abuse, trauma, and other related issues highlights the intricate nature of the difficulties that students confront and calls for holistic support and intervention programs (Chow et al., 2020). On the other hand, other departments, such as Teacher Education and Office Administration, placed LGBTQ+ topics lower on the priority list, suggesting that their program may not adequately address these issues. As Watkins et al. (2012) mentioned in their study, the variation in how mental health concerns are prioritized highlights the need for continuous assessments and flexible support services to ensure they remain responsive to the changing needs of every individual. By recognizing the different mental health priorities of every department, Bacolod City College can better tailor its support services, promoting a healthier and more supportive campus environment for all students.

Differences in Quality of Life (QoL) while living with mental health issues based on Demographic Variables. Based on Table 2 below, Older students, aged 22 years old and above, have a very good quality of life ($M=3.26$, $SD=0.65$) while living with mental health issues. Males also have a very good quality of life ($M=3.43$, $SD=0.65$); so do students living with their immediate family ($M=3.31$, $SD=0.53$), and those with families with lower-middle income ($M=3.26$, $SD=0.71$) and high income ($M=3.60$, $SD=0.55$). On the same table, Sex ($U=8925.5$, $p<0.001$), Living Condition ($H[2]=11.23$, $p=0.004$), and Employment of Parents ($F[3]=2.93247$, $p=0.0335$) are the demographic variables found to have significant differences in Quality of Life (QoL) when living with Mental Health Issues.

The idea of quality of life (QOL) is based on Maslow's theory of self-actualization and pertains to an individual's journey towards happiness and their true self (Tripathi, 2018). It includes the attainment of a person's essential needs like safety, belonging, and self-worth, which ultimately leads to the achievement of self-actualization and general well-being. This study finds the need to examine quality of life to properly understand the influence of demographic variables. This is because doing so can aid in the creation of specialized interventions and support that will improve the academic performance and general well-being of students. Furthermore, exploring quality of life (QoL) can highlight potential differences and guide school administrators and mental health professionals in creating the right resources and services to address the diverse needs of students living with mental health issues.

Table 2 presents data that reveals the significant differences in the quality of life (QoL) of students who are living with mental health issues based on demographic variables such as sex, living conditions, and the employment status of parents. The quality of life reported by students living in the immediate family was higher than among those who lived with relatives or in other accommodations such as

apartments, dorms, and boarding houses. Likewise, males reported a greater quality of life as compared to females. In addition, the quality of life for those whose parents were not employed was less pronounced compared to students whose parents had been employed. On the other hand, there was no significant difference in students' quality of life concerning age or family income, indicating that other demographic variables may not have a significant influence on students' quality of life.

Table 2. Differences in QoL when living with Mental Health Issues based on Demographic Variables

Demographic Variables	Means (SD)	Interpretation	Statistic	p-value
Age			U=17471	0.073
Older (≥ 22)	3.26 (0.65)	Very Good QoL		
Younger (< 22)	3.13 (0.67)	Good QoL		
*Sex			U=8925.5	<0.001
Male	3.43 (0.65)	Very Good QoL		
Female	3.12 (0.65)	Good QoL		
*Living Condition			H[2]=11.23	0.004
Living with Immediate Family	3.31 (0.53)	Very Good QoL		
Living with a Relative/ Extended Family	2.91 (0.97)	Good QoL		
Living in Apartment/ Dormitory/ Boarding House	3.06 (0.71)	Good QoL		
Family Income			F[3]=0.65211	0.5820
Poor	3.20 (0.67)	Good QoL		
Low Income	3.19 (0.61)	Good QoL		
Lower Middle Income	3.26 (0.71)	Very Good QoL		
High Income	3.60 (0.55)	Very Good QoL		
*Employment of Parents			F[3]=2.93247	0.0335
Both Employed	3.24 (0.56)	Good QoL		
Both Unemployed	2.96 (0.94)	Good QoL		
Care-off Guardian/ No Parents	3.30 (0.61)	Good QoL		
One (1) Working Parent	3.24 (0.61)	Good QoL		

Note. QoL- Quality of Life for those students with mental health issues. U statistic is Mann-Whitney U-test; H- kruskal-Wallis; F-ANOVA; Post-hoc test indicates Living with Immediate Family has significantly higher QoL versus those Living with a relative; while, Care-off Guardian has significantly higher QoL than having unemployed parents. Only those with asterisk (*) are found to have significant within group differences.

Older students—22 years of age and up—report a higher quality of life (QoL). This could be attributed to their increased maturity and life experience, which can lead to improved coping strategies and easier access to resources like independent living and stable housing (Arnett, 2015). Additionally, this age group might have more developed social networks and support systems that offer them practical and emotional help, improving their overall quality of life (La Guardia et al., 2021). Furthermore, older students could have a stronger sense of self and purpose, which might improve their well-being and capacity to deal with obstacles in life. A higher quality of life gives students a better chance to cope with stress, keep their mental health in check, and achieve both emotional and academic results. This positive state can encourage resilience and adaptation strategies, allowing them to cope more effectively with future challenges than in the past (Keyes, 2007). On the other hand, younger students should focus on building strong networks of support and developing deep connections with their peers, mentors, and families to achieve the same high quality of life. Younger students can also benefit from resilience-building initiatives, stress management instruction, and mental health resources to help them deal with the demands of both their personal and academic lives (Conley et al., 2017). Stressing the value of self-care routines like consistent exercise, mindfulness, and enough sleep can improve the quality of life and general well-being of younger kids.

Furthermore, a significant difference in quality of life (QoL) between male and female students living with mental health issues was found in this study. Males report a higher quality of life than females, possibly because of stronger social support networks and societal norms that emphasize emotional resilience in males (Seidler et al., 2016). However, compared to men, women may have particular stressors associated with managing a variety of obligations and cultural demands, which may affect their quality of life (Rice et al., 2016). Moreover, anxiety and sadness may be more common in women, which could lower their quality of life (Kuehner, 2017). Support systems, mental health services, and stress reduction programs should be specifically designed to address these issues to enhance the quality of life for female students.

In addition, living conditions were also found to have a significant difference in the quality of life of the respondents, as those living with immediate family report a higher quality of life than those who do not. This can be because family members offer emotional support and stability, which can mitigate the detrimental consequences of mental health problems and promote well-being (La Guardia et al., 2021). In the study of McPherson et al. (2016), it was found that close family members can provide comfort and resources like financial support and guidance, as well as help lessen feelings of isolation and loneliness. All of these things are critical for maintaining mental health. In contrast, this close support system may not be available to students who live with relatives or in other accommodations and could lead to a lower quality of life and possible exposure to additional stress factors such as roommate problems and lack of privacy (Jungbluth et al., 2018).

Finally, the employment status of parents shows a significant impact on the quality of life of the respondents. Findings in this study show that those whose parents are both unemployed report a lower quality of life. Uncertainty and stress brought on by the unemployment of parents can impair the student's ability to focus on their academic and personal goals, cause financial instability, and

worsen pre-existing mental health conditions (Seaward, 2020). Contrariwise, the financial security that comes with having both parents working can give a person a safe and supportive environment that meets their emotional and psychological needs, improving their resilience and quality of life (Conley et al., 2017).

The results of this study highlight how important it is to take demographics into account when assessing and helping individuals who are struggling with mental health concerns. Improving one's quality of life (QoL) and supporting them in their academic achievement and general well-being can be accomplished by designing interventions to address social and financial inequalities. Financial aid, mentorship programs, and counseling services are a few examples of programs and policies that offer targeted support and can lessen the negative effects of financial instability while also improving students' quality of life. Furthermore, providing career guidance and job placement assistance can assist students in obtaining internships or part-time jobs, which will enhance their financial status and resource accessibility (Chow et al., 2019). To foster an inclusive environment that supports all students, especially those from underprivileged backgrounds, institutions can also carry out extensive campaigns to raise awareness of mental health issues and offer easily available mental health treatments (Lipson et al., 2019). Teachers and administrators may guarantee that students with mental health concerns receive the assistance they require to succeed both academically and personally by taking proactive measures to address these variables.

Differences in the Students' Family Environment by Demographic Variables. For this portion of the study, the authors highlight the interpretation column of Table 3. The interpretation refers to the degree to which the student's familial environment understands or comprehends their mental health concerns and issues. Table 3 below, shows that the family environments of male students have a very good understanding of their mental health issues ($M=3.41$, $SD=0.75$). Similarly, students with High Income ($M=3.80$, $SD=0.44$) and students whose parents are both employed ($M=3.26$, $SD=0.75$) also have family environments that have a very good understanding of their mental health issues. Inferentially, age and sex are the only variables that have within-group significant differences ($U=12438.5$, $p=0.007$ and $U=9194$, $p=0.001$, respectively).

Table 3. Differences in Family Environment based on Demographic Variables

Demographic Variables	Means (SD)	Interpretation	Statistic	p-value
*Age			U=12438.5	0.007
Older (≥ 22)	3.20 (0.93)	Good		
Younger (< 22)	2.91 (1.05)	Good		
*Sex			U=9194	0.001
Male	3.41 (0.75)	Very Good		
Female	2.98 (1.03)	Good		
Living Condition			H[2]=2.401	0.301
Living with Immediate Family	3.06 (0.94)	Good		
Living with a Relative/ Extended Family	3.18 (1.10)	Good		
Living in Apartment/ Dormitory/ Boarding House	3.07 (1.09)	Good		
Family Income			F[3]=1.99532	0.1143
Poor	3.12 (0.93)	Good		
Low Income	2.93 (1.17)	Good		
Lower Middle Income	2.85 (1.13)	Good		
High Income	3.80 (0.44)	Very Good		
Employment of Parents			F[3]=1.2872	0.2785
Both Employed	3.26 (0.75)	Very Good		
Both Unemployed	2.98 (1.09)	Good		
Care-off Guardian/ No Parents	2.90 (1.24)	Good		
One (1) Working Parent	3.09 (0.98)	Good		

Note. Interpretation provides the descriptor of how well the students' family environment understands their mental health issues. U statistic is Mann-Whitney U-test; H- kruskal-Wallis; F-ANOVA. Only those with an asterisk (*) are found to have significant within-group differences.

Table 3 presents data that shows if there is a difference in the family environments of students based on demographic variables such as age, sex, living conditions, and family income. The findings show that there is a significant difference in the student's family environment if they are grouped according to age and sex. This result reveals that such factors in the life of an individual influence the level of understanding and support that the family could offer as regards the students' mental health issues. These are very important for the overall well-being of the student, for they can foster open communication, give access to resources that take care of one's mental health, and later on lead to emotional strength (La Guardia et al., 2021). This kind of family setup can boost a person's resilience, self-esteem, and academic performance as well as encourage help-seeking behaviors that are important in taking care of one's well-being (Gonzalez, 2021). For that reason, it is fundamental to give full attention to this issue, as it will significantly improve mental health, which in turn will improve a person's quality of life.

The findings show that older students have rated a higher result than the younger students in their family environment. It indicates that students of older ages have a family environment that offers more empathy for their mental health difficulties. This result is most likely the outcome of their life experiences which have allowed them to grow up and become more independent and mature as well as to acquire better coping mechanisms. These abilities have also helped them to be more eager to voice their concerns and get the help they need (Arnett, 2015). This can also boost their resilience, enhance their academic success, and enhance their mental health. In the study

of Gonzalez (2021), a loving and understanding family environment is beneficial to a person's well-being. On the other hand, students with ages younger than 22 may find it difficult to talk about their concerns because their family environment is less understanding and supportive of their mental health issues. There is a great risk in this because it could make their already-existing mental health conditions worse.

Next, the result of the study also presents sex as a factor that plays an important role in an individual's family environment. The family environment of male students conveyed a very good understanding of their mental health problems, compared to female students, who conveyed only a good understanding. This finding may have been affected by gender roles and some existing social norms that influence how families understand and support mental health issues. Males may receive more active support, as societies expect emotional resilience and less stigma around their mental health, which may lead to families being more attentive and addressing their own mental health needs (Seidler et al., 2016), while females may have problems speaking out because of various social pressures like concerns about being judged as vulnerable or overly emotional. This can hinder female students from receiving the support and understanding they need, which can increase the harm to their mental health and overall well-being. Addressing these gender differences in understanding mental health issues in families is critical to providing equitable support and resources for all students.

Finally, it is interesting to note that there were no significant differences found in the students' family environment when they were grouped according to the rest of the demographic factors, such as living conditions, family income, and parental employment. The findings indicate that these elements may not be equally significant in shaping the understanding of the family in the context of mental health. The lack of significant differences may also indicate that the effects of these factors are mediated by other aspects such as social support networks, community resources, and cultural attitudes toward mental health. As a result, even students from different backgrounds receive the same level of understanding and support from family members to meet their mental health needs. However, these findings highlight the need for further research on the complex interplay of various demographic factors and their possible indirect effects on family perceptions of student mental health problems.

The results highlight the importance of implementing targeted interventions to improve families' understanding of students' mental health problems, especially for female students under the age of 22, who may have more difficulties in that area. Educational programs that educate families about mental health issues and provide advice on how to help an individual address knowledge gaps and promote more honest dialogue. These interventions can create a more caring and supportive environment for students by providing families with the information and tools needed to effectively address mental health issues (La Guardia et al., 2021). In addition, providing students with mental health support and resources can empower them to ask for and seek help when needed and become more adept at facing obstacles, benefiting both their academic and personal development.

Overall, the study results show the extent of prioritization of mental health issues per department as well as provide an overview of how demographic variables influence the quality of life and understanding of the family environment of students with mental health issues. Factors such as age, gender, employment status of parents, and living conditions significantly affect the quality of life of students and the level of understanding and support they receive from their families. For instance, students older than 22 conveyed a higher quality of life and very good family support in understanding their mental health issues because of the greater independence that they were experiencing and their maturity (Arnett, 2015). Likewise, male students experienced stronger family support for their mental health problems, which may be the result of social expectations to provide them with more active support (Seidler et al., 2016). Although these findings align with the theoretical framework of this study, which emphasizes the importance of social and emotional support in improving the quality of life of students, there is still room for improvement in providing equal support to different populations.

The findings also support the study's theoretical framework based on the Social Ecological Model (SEM) of Urie Bronfenbrenner, which emphasizes the need to fulfill basic needs such as security, belonging, and self-esteem to achieve general well-being and self-actualization (Tripathi, 2018). The results may have achieved the goals of the social-ecological model to some extent by recognizing and addressing the differences in quality of life and the understanding of the family environment, particularly among groups of younger and female students with mental health problems. Specific interventions to meet the student's needs, including more educational programs for families and expanding mental health resources for everyone, are very essential to improving communication and support. The goals of the theoretical framework can be fully realized by giving attention to these differences, which in the long run will lead to a more encouraging and favorable avenue for students to attain overall well-being and academic success.

Conclusion

Every student has a unique set of mental health concerns and priorities. Nevertheless, to help students grow into better individuals and citizens of the nation, the Guidance Center of Bacolod City College should continue to support and handle these concerns. It's critical to keep an eye on the quality of life of students who are dealing with mental health concerns and to take into account their family context. The study also highlights the importance of providing equal support and resources to all students, although male students and older students appear to benefit more. By recognizing and addressing these disparities, academic institutions, mental health professionals, and even our public officials can develop support systems that better respond to the needs of diverse populations, thereby promoting inclusive and healthy learning environments.

This study provides a significant overview of the challenges faced by students with mental health issues and the factors that affect their quality of life and family environment. This study is important for understanding the specific needs of students at Bacolod City College, given the importance of a supportive educational environment for their overall well-being and academic success.

Limitation

Some limitations of the findings are also acknowledged in the study. Some demographic factors that are also significant, such as individual differences in mental health problems and cultural or ethnic differences among students, which may likewise affect the quality of life and family environments, were not included. Moreover, the self-reported measures may introduce biases and may not accurately reveal the variety of beliefs, behaviors, or experiences that every student has. Lastly, the cross-sectional nature of the study limits the ability to determine causal relationships. Future studies are needed to fully understand these associations, especially studies that follow students over longer periods.

Despite these limitations, this study has significant practical value in guiding the development of targeted support strategies for students with mental health problems. The findings will allow the creation of educational initiatives and mental health resources designed to cater to student needs, thus promoting a more supportive and inclusive learning environment by identifying key demographic differences.

Application

One of the ultimate goals of Bacolod City College is to offer its students comprehensive, complete, and specialized mental health programs, aiming to increase the student's overall well-being and resilience to advance in their personal, emotional, intellectual, and social lives in preparation for their future lives.

From the results of this study, the following working programs are the recommended initiatives that can be implemented to cater to the mental health issues or concerns of the Bacolod City College student body. These endeavors have the potential to foster mental health literacy among faculty members, students, and their families and build a more encouraging environment that will surely benefit everybody.

The Mental Health Series.

A.1. LGBTQ+ with GAD Awareness

Addressing LGBTQ+ with GAD awareness in student activities is essential to creating a safe and inclusive environment for all students. Although it is a low priority for Office Administration and Teacher Education Departments, it should be seen as a need for strengthening awareness. By educating students about gender and sexual diversity, as well as generalized anxiety disorder (GAD), schools can promote acceptance, understanding, and empathy among peers. This can help reduce stigma and discrimination towards LGBTQ+ individuals and those struggling with anxiety disorders.

A.2. Depression and Anxiety Avenues

Depression and anxiety avenues should also be emphasized in student activities to raise awareness about the prevalence of these mental health conditions. By providing information about the signs and symptoms of depression and anxiety, students can learn how to recognize when they or their peers may be struggling and how to seek help. Additionally, promoting healthy coping mechanisms and stress management techniques can empower students to take control of their mental well-being. It is a high priority for almost all departments of Bacolod City College.

A.3. Suicide and Self-Injury

Suicide and self-injury prevention activities are crucial in schools to address the serious consequences of untreated mental health issues. By teaching students about the warning signs of suicide and self-harm, as well as how to intervene and support someone in crisis, schools can help prevent tragedies and save lives. Encouraging open communication and destigmatizing seeking help for mental health concerns are key components of suicide prevention efforts. Most Business Education students in the city college are interested in this.

A.4. HIV and STDs

HIV and STD education is another important aspect of promoting mental health and wellness among students. By raising awareness about the risks of unprotected sex, the importance of regular testing, and the stigma surrounding HIV and STDs, schools can empower students to make informed decisions about their sexual health. Encouraging open and honest conversations about sexual health can help reduce the spread of infections and promote healthy relationships. Most Business Education students in the city college are interested in this.

A.5. Family Issues

Family issues are also significant factors that can impact students' mental health and well-being. By addressing topics such as family dynamics, communication skills, and conflict resolution strategies, schools can help students navigate challenges at home and build healthy relationships with their families. Providing access to family counseling and support services can further assist students in coping

with family-related stressors. Most Business Education students in the city college are interested in this.

A.6. Counseling

Incorporating counseling services into student activities is essential for providing additional support to those in need. By offering individual and group counseling sessions, schools can help students process their emotions, develop coping skills, and build resilience in the face of adversity. Counseling services can also serve as a valuable resource for students experiencing mental health crises or in need of ongoing support.

Sectoral Orientation Service

B.1. Female Students. A specialized series of meetings and activities are to be prepared for the empowerment and support of students, particularly younger and female students, who might have experienced greater challenges in terms of their quality of life and their families' comprehension of mental health issues.

B.2. Involvement of Parents/ Guardians. Bacolod City College has to organize programs for families, especially for parents and guardians of the students, that inform and increase their knowledge about mental health as well as offer advice on how to properly support their children, especially those who are experiencing mental health issues.

Social Services Collaboration

C.1. On Abuse and Trauma. Abuse and trauma awareness activities can help students understand the impact of trauma on mental health and well-being. By educating students about different forms of abuse, such as physical, emotional, and sexual abuse, as well as the long-term effects of trauma, schools can create a supportive environment for survivors. Providing resources for counseling and support services is essential for students who have experienced abuse or trauma.

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